

THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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INTRODUCTION

One of the main goals of building a socially oriented market economy in Uzbekistan is the priority development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country. To achieve this goal, economic reforms have been carried out, and large institutional frameworks have been created to enhance its role. These include legal and regulatory documents governing the organization of entrepreneurial activity, non-governmental organizations and enterprises that support entrepreneurs. The establishment of a complex of private entrepreneurship and small business in Uzbekistan is progressing well.

One of the main ways to strengthen the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its comprehensive development, and accelerate the transition to a market economy, in particular, is the development

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role and reform of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan, further stabilization and growth of today's private enterprises, the extent to which the potential of small business has increased.

of small business and private entrepreneurship. Therefore, a number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted on the development of entrepreneurship, its support by the state, the initiative and encouragement of private entrepreneurship. It is difficult to imagine the fundamental basis of economic and social reforms in our country without entrepreneurship, efficiency and business acumen. The development of free market relations is reflected in people's lives, their lifestyles, spiritual and life skills. Support for small business and private entrepreneurship not only achieves economic goals related to the sustainable development of the economy, the improvement of economic relations, the development of competition and the filling of the consumer market.

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Uzbekistan is the priority development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country. To achieve this goal, economic reforms have been carried out, and a large institutional framework has been created to enhance its role. These include legal and regulatory documents governing the organization of entrepreneurial activity, non-governmental organizations and enterprises that assist entrepreneurs. The establishment of a complex of private entrepreneurship and small business in Uzbekistan is progressing well. Small businesses can create jobs independently of the state, that is, without large capital investments, reduce the temporary shortage of existing goods, and even eliminate this shortage completely. In today's society, small businesses need to be focused on meeting the needs of individuals. This is especially true in the field of consumer services and consumer goods. Small businesses also play an important role in introducing technology innovations.

Preliminary research in the field of legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity was conducted by a lawyer B.Ibratov. He argues that all the actions of the entrepreneur are mainly the analysis of market opportunities, their use, the implementation of innovative ideas, not the traditional class definition of the entrepreneur leading to the essence of capitalist exploitation, but its function in this area of human activity. lib explains the need to focus on its place in society and its social significance. The entrepreneur also describes it as a set of organizational, economic, financial, legal and other economic relations that provide services for reproduction in individual segments of a market economy.

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Over the years, more than 50 Presidential decrees and resolutions have been adopted to provide comprehensive support to entrepreneurship. In particular, the procedures for state registration of business activities, obtaining various permits and many other services have been simplified and convenience has been created for the population. To this end, the Public Service Agency and its field centers have been established and launched. In order to protect the rights and legitimate interests of business entities, the position of Business Ombudsman was introduced and launched. The Prime Minister's Office has been established in all regions to receive and resolve appeals of business entities. The State Fund for Entrepreneurship Development under the Cabinet of Ministers was established with 200 billion soums and \$ 50 million. In addition, the volume of loans provided by commercial banks to entrepreneurs has been increased and is being provided to the population. Such practical measures are bearing fruit. Small business accounts for about 60 percent of the country's gross domestic product, a third of industrial output, 98 percent of agricultural output, and half of investment. In most regions, small businesses account for 70-90 percent of exports

Features of small business and private entrepreneurship (small working capital, its rapid turnover, the ability to quickly replace the means of production, etc.) allow it to have several advantages:

- research, delivery and development of new products, their production in small associations, taking into account the risk of rapid changes in demand;

- Reliability of fast technical service and strong communication with customers;
- flexible organization of production and sales in accordance with market requirements and changes in market conditions;
- absorption of excess labor;
- Simplicity of management, lack of large administrative apparatus, short lead time in the development of construction and design capacity, rapid payback of capital expenditures, high speed of capital turnover;
- fuller and more efficient use of raw materials and labor resources, industrial waste.

Small business and private entrepreneurship, and everything related to it, is an important and integral part of the organizational structure of modern social production. Therefore, small business and private entrepreneurship play an important role in the development of our economy and are supported by the state.

Private entrepreneurship and small business are finding their place in the context of accelerating the development of science and technology, the transition to new technologies in advanced industries. Such entrepreneurship is an integral part of the whole system, providing new information technologies, new ideas and modernization of production. In addition, small businesses are one of the preferred forms of production in high-risk conditions. Small businesses also play an important role in introducing technological innovations. Small businesses, which adopt new technological ideas faster than large enterprises, have less risk and can start work faster than large-scale production. This can help in the development of

scientific and technological progress in our conditions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

An industry-wide analysis of the above items shows that we can see a relatively low level of small business in an industrial sector where the efficiency of job creation compared to other sectors is high. Maintaining the current growth rate could lead to problems with future growth in wages and real incomes from entrepreneurship. This situation may lead to the restriction of social guarantees provided by the state to the population. In addition, the share of small businesses in sales remains high. In the retail trade turnover, we can see that the share of small businesses and micro-firms was 20.2%, while the share of individual entrepreneurs was 69.4%, which has a negative impact on cash inflows to the banking sector. and inconsistencies in the tax base of small businesses.

As a result of radical reforms to support entrepreneurs and improve the business environment, Uzbekistan rose 7 places to 69th place in the World Bank's Doing Business 2020 report and was named one of the world's top 20 reformers. took place in the ranks of the state. For the first time, our country has risen to eighth place in the world in terms of ease of starting a new business. As a result of such opportunities, 91,000 new business entities were created in the last 10 months of this year, or twice as many as in 2018. However, it should be noted that there is still much to be done for the development of the industry. In particular, it is necessary to address the shortcomings identified in the report "Doing Business 2020", including the creation of facilities for land allocation, construction and registration of

property. Therefore, it is necessary to provide entrepreneurs with land through online auctions, to provide electronic inter-agency information exchange on property registration. Based on foreign experience, it is also important to create a separate structure responsible for the independent registration of property rights.

Small business and private entrepreneurship play an important role in ensuring the overall development of the economy and overcoming the shortage of goods and services. The creation of a system of small enterprises in Uzbekistan in the conditions of rapid growth of labor resources and the specificity of the location of production creates the following opportunities:

the introduction of free labor resources, new economic relations, the emergence of new forms of ownership, greater involvement of people released in production in social production, the emergence of new forms of ownership;

raising the material, spiritual and professional level of the population, especially the youth;

Bringing industrial production closer to residential areas, taking into account the low mobility of the population, and more fully meet the needs of the population in consumer goods;

Restoration of national and artistic handicrafts, as well as assistance in the development of small and medium-sized cities, rural settlements, in general, increase the efficiency of the economy, which is very important for each region.

While acknowledging the positive role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the development of the economy, it is also wrong to overestimate its importance. Private

entrepreneurship can be active only to a certain extent, so it is necessary to create the necessary conditions for the development of small business. For this, in our opinion, it is necessary to create financial funds. These funds should be a guarantee for entrepreneurs to obtain soft loans in commercial banks, and serve as a source of subsidies, including non-repayable subsidies (for the development of enterprises in certain priority sectors of the economy).

Improving the system of financial support for small businesses in Uzbekistan should be aimed at stimulating the activities of banks, foundations, investments and insurance companies that provide services to small businesses and private entrepreneurship. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in other countries, the company can receive soft loans if it participates in the priority state program (creation of new equipment, development of remote areas, etc.). At the same time, the minimum interest rate and long-term repayment are the main conditions for lending.

The activities of small businesses are greatly affected by a variety of unpredictable risks, sudden changes in the situation, insolvency of customers, natural disasters that put them in a difficult situation. Therefore, the insurance system in developed countries is well established. It is necessary to establish insurance in our country as well. This system should ensure a favorable environment for the development of small businesses (especially in areas with high commercial risks), create confidence and the necessary stability for entrepreneurs who own or start a venture with borrowed capital.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, increasing the contribution of small business to the country's economy, creating small industrial zones, improving the investment climate and competitive environment, expanding public procurement in the framework of public-private partnerships with small businesses. It should be noted that it is important to provide financial support to successful and promising small enterprises that have sufficient export potential, but at the same

time do not have sufficient capital for further development. These measures will help create more jobs in the effective small business sector, increase access to world markets, increase the country's export potential and increase incomes. In short, the development of entrepreneurship and small business in our country today remains one of the priorities of public policy. In the words of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, we can achieve development and a prosperous life only through active entrepreneurship, hard work and aspiration.

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